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Soil carbon losses due to priming moderated by adaptation and legacy effects

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Abstract

Increasing soil organic carbon contents contributes to global climate change mitigation. However, new plant inputs can enhance the mineralization of native soil organic carbon by the positive priming effect, which may counterbalance the sequestration of new carbon. Here we use soils from a 20 year chronosequence of inverted pasture soils (reciprocal translocation of topsoil and subsoil to >1 m) to study the dynamics of soil organic carbon in topsoils and subsoils. We evaluated the root-induced priming effect by differentiating native soil organic carbon from ^{13}C root-derived carbon in a 6 month incubation experiment. We found that the addition of fresh root-derived carbon caused positive priming of native soil organic carbon in new topsoils ($109 \pm 27\%$ additional respiration compared with controls without roots) and subsoils ($331 \pm 84\%$) after inversion. This effect was temporary for new topsoils as they accumulated soil organic carbon and adapted to high carbon inputs within a few years, leading to no priming in the long term. In contrast, buried topsoils became more sensitive to root carbon inputs over time, demonstrating how the legacy of high carbon inputs mediates the magnitude of priming (50% to 390% after 20 years of inversion). Overall, carbon losses with priming never exceeded new root-derived carbon inputs. We conclude that priming is a temporary reaction to additional carbon, which attenuates when soils adapt to high carbon inputs within a few years to decades.

Globally soils store around 3,200 Pg of carbon (C) as soil organic carbon (SOC) in the upper three meters, with 40-70% being located in subsoils below 30 cm depth^{1,2}. The sequestration of SOC has the potential to contribute to climate change mitigation, while supporting essential soil ecosystem services³⁻⁶. Subsoils, in particular, may offer a large sequestration potential, due to their generally low SOC contents and long SOC turnover times^{7,8}. Consequently, increasing the organic matter inputs to subsoils by, for example, deep rooting plants has been suggested as climate mitigation practice⁹⁻¹¹. However, such plant inputs may also stimulate microbial activity in subsoils and trigger enhanced mineralization of long preserved native SOC, which is conceptualized as the priming effect. The priming effect can be positive or negative by enhancing or reducing the mineralization of native SOC¹². A broad range of outcomes, from >400% positive^{13,14} to >50% negative^{15,16} priming and large variations with land-use¹⁷⁻¹⁹ have been reported, indicating the potential for large changes in SOC mineralization with the addition of fresh organic matter. Generally, topsoils with higher SOC contents and continuous fresh organic matter inputs are considered to be less susceptible to priming²⁰. Subsoils with low SOC contents, however, are hypothesized to be much more susceptible to positive priming as fresh input of organic matter acts as energy and nutrient source for substrate limited microbial communities^{21,22}. A better understanding of the conditions that determine positive and negative priming is needed to estimate the soil's C sequestration potential over the long-term, particularly in subsoils^{21,23,24}, and predict how C farming practices may contribute to climate change mitigation.

Assessing priming effects is methodologically challenging. Most previous studies have used single saccharides, such as glucose or cellulose, or dried plant material to quantify the priming effect (e.g. ^{14,15,17,21,25,26}). These additions are far from natural conditions and exclude the effect of living roots, as the main source of organic matter in grasslands and subsoils, on native SOC mineralization²⁷⁻²⁹. Input of roots and exudates can alter soil physiochemical conditions (e.g. pH, water content, redox potential, nutrient and oxygen availability)^{8,30,31}, which can directly

and indirectly affect microbial community composition and activity³²⁻³⁴, ultimately altering native SOC mineralization on small-scale³⁵. The extent to which additional inputs of root-derived C may destabilize native SOC in the long-term is unclear^{8,30}.

We used a chronosequence spanning 20 years of deeply inverted (1.2-1.8 m) temperate pasture soils with similar soil properties as a model system to assess root-induced priming compared to non-inverted developed soils (Fig. 1 a&b; Table S1 and methods for details)³⁶. Deep soil inversion is a form of soil modification that involves a single deep ploughing or excavation of the soil, which buries topsoil and brings subsoil to the surface³⁶⁻³⁸. It is practiced in many parts of the globe to reverse soil compaction, improve water infiltration and drainage, and bury weeds, with the aim of increasing pasture or crop production and preparing soil for afforestation. The burial of SOC-rich topsoil in the subsoil (henceforth “new subsoil”; Extended Data Figure 1a) can slow the decomposition of the buried SOC and increase the total SOC stock by 42-70% compared to non-inverted soil^{36,37,39,40}. Inverted subsoils, which form the new surface (henceforth “new topsoil”), were initially low in C, but rapidly accumulated SOC (e.g. 1.2-1.8 Mg SOC ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in 0-15 cm depth) to gradually form C-rich topsoils under pasture³⁶. In an extensive laboratory experiment, we grew ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.) under continuous 10%-¹³C₂ enriched atmosphere to achieve traceable below ground inputs of root-derived organic matter (3.3 ± 0.8 mg C (g soil)⁻¹; 2.3 ± 0.2 atom% ¹³C). Following removal of the aboveground biomass, we incubated the new and non-inverted topsoils and subsoils with roots and root-free controls over six months (164-days) to evaluate root biomass-induced priming of native SOC and changes in total SOC (see methods for details; Extended Data Figure 1b&c). The ¹³C enrichment allowed us to separate root-derived C from native SOC in respired CO₂-C and bulk SOC fractions. The chronosequence enabled us to examine how C inputs from roots affected the priming responses of new topsoils and subsoils at different stages of development after inversion compared to non-inverted long-term pasture soils. Thus, the new topsoils served as a SOC accumulation sequence of two decades to investigate if and when the soils might

adapt to fresh C inputs and how priming responses shift over time. The new subsoils were used to identify if a legacy effect, due to former high C inputs, is maintained equivalent to non-inverted topsoils.

Adaptation of soils to priming with C inputs

We found that new root-derived organic matter inputs induced strong positive priming effects with up to six times higher native SOC respiration rates compared to soils without roots (Fig. 1c&d, Fig. 2). The highest root-induced increase in native SOC respiration was found in the non-inverted low SOC subsoils, which were previously isolated from direct root C inputs. In contrast, there was no evidence of root-induced priming of native SOC in non-inverted topsoils, which had been continuously exposed to plant C inputs under pasture for >20 years and had the highest SOC and microbial biomass contents (Fig. 1a and Fig. 2). The new topsoils that developed following inversion (3-20 years), gradually adapted to new root inputs and positive priming decreased significantly from $175 \pm 22\%$ three years after inversion to $64 \pm 13\%$ in more developed topsoils 20 years after inversion (Fig. 2). Although the total respiration was similar for all new topsoils ($3.8 \pm 0.1 \text{ mg CO}_2\text{-C (g soil)}^{-1}$; Extended Data Figure 2 a&b and Fig. S1 a&b), the proportion of respired native SOC decreased with time after inversion (Fig. 1c). Twenty years after soil inversion, the native SOC in the new topsoil was still more susceptible to positive priming by roots compared to non-inverted topsoils, where no priming was observed. This is consistent with the lower SOC contents (-54%) and stocks (-36%) in the new topsoils, 20 years after inversion, compared to non-inverted topsoils, which were previously estimated to require around 40 years to fully recover after soil inversion³⁶. Extrapolations of the chronosequence results suggest that about 30 years would be required for the new topsoils to adapt to the root C inputs and reach negligible rates of priming similar to permanent non-inverted topsoils (Extended Data Figure 4a).

We hypothesize that the adaptation of new topsoils to fresh root-C inputs was linked to an increased microbial biomass after inversion (Fig. 1a). Within two decades, the adaptation may have resulted in microbial composition changes due to the continuous fresh litter input under grassland and pasture management⁴¹, and the microbial community became conditioned to the dominant and available C source^{42,43}. Therefore, priming appears to be a temporary phenomenon that occurs over years to decades following soil disturbance and diminishes as the microbial community adapts to a change in the source and quantity of organic matter.

Figure 1 | Soil organic carbon contents, microbial biomass and respiration of native SOC. The native SOC contents and microbial biomass (C_{mic}) of topsoils (a; 0-15 cm) and subsoils (b; 60 cm depth intervals; with n.d. indicates not detected biomass) are shown prior to the incubation and growth of roots (see methods and Table S1 for specific depths). The total native SOC respired from topsoils (c) and subsoils (d) after six months of incubation with and without (control) roots is expressed as the native SOC specific respiration. Significant differences between treatments with and without roots are indicated by asterisks (statistics are presented in Table S4; n.s. indicates no significant differences). All values are presented with the standard error of the mean of incubation replicates ($n=4$, also shown as circles). Total respirations are presented in Extended Data Figure 2. The cumulative fluxes and CO_2 -C production over the incubation experiment are shown in Extended Data Figure 3 and Fig. S1. Data

The legacy of C inputs controls priming

A legacy effect of fresh plant organic matter inputs to topsoils was maintained for three years in new subsoils but diminished with time after inversion (Fig 2). The low rate of root-induced priming ($50 \pm 2\%$; three years after inversion) increased with time since inversion to high priming of native SOC mineralization ($394 \pm 23\%$) in new subsoils created 20 years earlier (Fig. 1d and Fig. 2). This nearly matched the priming of native SOC measured in non-inverted subsoils ($434 \pm 34\%$), which had much lower SOC contents and were predominantly isolated from C inputs under pasture (Fig. 1b, Table S1). The exceptionally high positive priming effect recorded at the site seven years after inversion ($529 \pm 41\%$) did not align with the other chronosequence sites, which may be due to the exceptionally low subsoils C contents at this site (Fig. 1b and ref.³⁶) indicating higher dilution of the buried topsoil C with subsoil material, potentially accentuating the positive priming effects (Extended Data Figure 4b).

We found that the gradual increase in root-induced priming of native SOC respiration in new subsoils was not directly associated with a loss of SOC, since the SOC contents and fraction of free particulate organic matter (POM; Extended Data Figure 3) remained high after soil inversion over 20 years (Fig. 1b & Table S1)³⁶. The incubation conditions applied here are assumed to represent optimum priming responses as they were not constrained by field subsoil conditions, including low oxygen levels and temperature limitation. Furthermore, priming is not solely controlled by C but also available nutrients such as nitrogen¹². We adjusted available N (i.e. nitrate and ammonium) during ryegrass growth to reach similar nutrient availability along the chronosequence (see method section). Our findings support the concept that the persistence of SOC in subsoils is controlled by the decoupling from fresh plant-derived organic matter inputs⁴⁴, which act as an initiating energy source for the microbial community and facilitate native C mineralization^{21,45}. However, the burial of topsoils during soil inversion increased not only the SOC contents, but also the total soil microbial biomass in the new subsoil

(Fig. 1b). This highlights that even with high SOC contents and relatively high microbial biomass, the mineralization of fresh C can be inhibited.

Figure 2 | Priming effect with roots in topsoils and subsoils. The loss of native SOC due to root-induced priming in inverted soils is compared to root free non-inverted soils (grey shaded area). The soil organic carbon contents of the topsoils (0-15 cm) and subsoils (60 cm depth intervals) are indicated by the size of the circles (Fig. 1a&b). The gradual reduction in root-induced priming of native SOC in the new topsoils (shown in green) proceeds as they adapt to higher SOC inputs under pasture. In comparison, the gradual increase in root-induced priming of native SOC respiration in new subsoils (shown in yellow) indicates initial legacy effects that are lost as the soils adapt to low C inputs over 20 years. Linear regressions fitted to the data are shown in Extended Data Figure 4. All values are shown with standard error of the mean of incubation replicates (n=4).

The fate of fresh roots explains priming mechanisms

Of the total added root-derived C ($3.3 \pm 0.8 \text{ mg C (g soil)}^{-1}$), one-third ($31 \pm 2\%$) was recovered as POM and mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) immediately after completing the growth and ^{13}C labeling of the ryegrass (Fig. S3, Table S2). The majority of added root-derived C ($69 \pm 2\%$) was in the coarse fraction ($>2 \text{ mm}$) at the start of the incubation with similar distribution for all soils. While POM is generally regarded as biologically labile, MAOM is regarded to be more stable and contribute to a longer-term C sequestration^{8,46-48}. This suggests that substantial proportions of root-derived C can rapidly bind to mineral surfaces during plant

growth of 22 days ($16 \pm 1\%$ of total root-derived C in MAOM), potentially stabilizing the new SOC in slow-cycling fractions and contributing to the potential long-term sequestration of root-derived organic matter^{34,49–51}.

After six months of incubation, root-derived C contributed to 54–80% of the total CO₂-C respired from new and non-inverted topsoils (Extended Data Figure 3 and Table S3). The proportion of root-derived C in total respired CO₂-C was similar for the non-inverted topsoil and the newly formed subsoil (three years after inversion). However, it was lower for the non-inverted subsoil and new subsoils formed between seven and 20 years (34–50% of total respired CO₂-C). Consequently, root mineralization would likely continue for more than six months under favorable incubation conditions and may prolong the priming effect in new subsoils formed more than three years after inversion.

More than half of the remaining root-derived C after the incubation was mineral-associated in the non-inverted topsoil (57%) and new subsoil (62%) formed three years after inversion (Fig. 3). The high percentages of root-derived C in the MAOM fractions suggest that C stabilization may initially be faster in soils receiving continuously high C inputs, due to the observed higher rates of new plant C turnover, compared to soils conditioned to low C inputs⁵². This apparent rapid stabilization and transfer of root-derived C to mineral fractions remained as a legacy in the new subsoil formed three years after inversion. In the subsoils (non-inverted and new subsoils created between seven to 20 years), most of the root-derived C remained in coarse fractions (up to 68%) and its proportions in the POM fractions decreased (Fig. 3 and Extended Data Figure 5). This is since subsoil is disconnected from continuous inputs. The large fraction of undecomposed roots in these subsoils may indicate a temporal delay of fresh organic matter cycling compared to the rapid decomposition of roots in non-inverted topsoils experiencing continuously high C inputs (Fig. 3a and Fig. S3a). The transfer of new root-derived C into the MAOM fractions was lower where the new subsoil had been isolated from root-C inputs for longer than three years and lowest in the non-inverted subsoil, which was

always isolated (only 25% of root-derived C remained; Fig. 3). Consequently, subsoils adapted to high C input may not be affected by priming, and long-term sequestration by mineral-stabilization may outweigh priming-induced losses of native SOC.

Tracing root-derived C along the chronosequence of inverted and non-inverted pasture soils allowed us to disentangle and improve our mechanistic understanding of root-induced priming effects on SOC storage and loss. Based on our findings, we consider that a spatial separation of roots and the microbial community at an earlier stage of new topsoil development, which remained on the microscale after homogenization of the soils (see method section), may have limited the root mineralization. Spatial separation of the microbial community from readily available substrates is considered as a key mechanism affecting SOC persistence^{44,53,54}. This spatial separation can inhibit the development of a microbial network that constrains its community composition and functionality^{55,56}. The small-scale heterogeneity allowed coarse roots to persist during the incubation in new topsoils (Fig. 3a), leading to a gradual adaptation and conditioning of the microbial community to fresh plant C inputs along the chronosequence, ultimately reducing native SOC mineralization (Fig. 2)⁵⁵. The rapid mineralization of roots in soils adapted to high C inputs (Fig. 3), e.g. non-inverted topsoil and new subsoil (three years after inversion), suggest that spatial constraints are negligible and adaptation is predominately controlled by the capacity of the microbial community to process fresh organic matter sources. The persistence of SOC by spatial separation is generally more predominant in subsoils where the microbial community is isolated to hot spots determined by local C and nutrient availability^{28,56}. The high proportion of coarse roots remaining and limited transfer of root-derived C to POM and MAOM in non-inverted subsoil supports this theory of spatial separation in low C subsoils (Fig. 3a). However, the increasing recovery of undecomposed roots in new subsoils more than three years after inversion, with high SOC contents and microbial biomass suggest that the microbial functionality to acquire fresh organic matter is suppressed when the soil is disconnected from continuous organic matter inputs. Therefore, the legacy effect of high

C inputs and the soil's adaptation is independent of the total SOC and microbial biomass pool and implies that priming is predominantly controlled by rate and continuity of fresh organic matter inputs.

Figure 3 | Allocation of root-derived C within fractions. The proportion root-derived C remaining as coarse root (> 2 mm; **a**) and mineral associated organic matter (**b**) in topsoils and subsoils after six months of incubation. Grey arrows indicate the legacy effect of C inputs in subsoils within the first few years after inversion and adaptation to low C inputs over longer periods (**a**). A lower rate of fresh root mineralization with time since inversion resulted in less transfer of fresh root-C into the mineral associated fraction where the soil has been decoupled from fresh C inputs (**b**). The proportion of root-derived C in the particulate organic matter is shown in Extended Data Figure 5 and the proportion of root derived C after the growth of the ryegrass (pre-incubation) in Table S2. Linear regressions with time since inversion are shown in Fig. S4. Fractionation was performed on composites of the incubation replicates (n=4; see method section).

Implications for carbon sequestration

The findings of this study have important practical implications for sequestration of SOC in subsoils. The propagation of deep-rooting plants to increase subsoil C sequestration^{9,11} may trigger short-term losses of native subsoil SOC through priming. However, we provide evidence that subsoils can adapt to high C inputs over time, which reduces the priming of native SOC mineralization and may enhance the stabilization of root-derived C. Alternatively, the burial of

C-rich topsoils in subsoils by natural depositional erosion or where soil profiles are modified by, for example, full inversion tillage^{37–39,57} may serve to decouple the buried C from the priming induced by fresh inputs of root-derived C in the surface soils. The buried C, however, may become more vulnerable to priming over time as it loses the ability to process fresh C inputs after an initial legacy effect.

We found that the addition of fresh root-derived C never resulted in net losses of total C after six months of incubation, despite the positive priming responses (Fig. 4, Table S3). In 50% of the soils tested, the addition of root-derived C resulted in significant C gains (0.1–1.6 mg C (g soil)⁻¹). The magnitude of C gain and the here identified adaptation and legacy effect will be controlled by biogeochemical soil properties and pedo-climatic conditions in other regions than studied here. By retaining all these factors constant along the chronosequence (see method section), we were able to identify C changes on a decadal scale under optimum and controlled conditions. Our findings clearly show that independent of the initial SOC content, microbial biomass and the history of C inputs, root-derived C inputs can promote increases in total SOC. Particularly high positive net C balances were found in the soils that were conditioned to high C inputs. In soils that have long been disconnected from fresh C inputs, e.g. non-inverted subsoil, or that have not adapted to extensive priming and native SOC mineralization was compensated by the large proportion of remaining uncomposed roots (Fig. 4b). These results highlight that both, priming and sequestration, should be considered as complementary and not opposing processes and roots provide a large potential for net C gain in soils.

Figure 4 | Gain of root-derived C and loss of native SOC with net balance. Positive values indicate the net gain in root-derived C and negative values show the loss of native SOC after six months of incubation for topsoils (a) and subsoils (b). The gains of root-derived C are portioned among coarse roots (>2 mm), particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral associated organic matter (MAOM) as calculated with the proportions of root-derived C derived from one composite per sample after incubation and the total respiration of each replicate. The sum of all fractions represents the total root-derived C remaining (Table S2). The relative distribution of respired root-derived C and its distribution in fractions is presented in Fig. S63. Significant gain of root-derived C is indicated with asterisks (statistics are presented in Table S5). All values are shown with the standard error of the mean of incubation replicates (n=4) and relative proportions obtained from fractionation.

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Authors contribution

M.S. conceptualized and designed the experiment with, A.D., M.H.B. and S.A.. M.S. conducted the experiment and performed all laboratory analyses. M.S. conducted the data analysis and wrote the manuscript with contributions from all authors. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

References

1. Batjes, N. H. Harmonized soil property values for broad-scale modelling (WISE30sec) with estimates of global soil carbon stocks. *Geoderma* **269**, 61–68 (2016).
2. Jobbágy, B. E. G. & Jackson, R. The vertical distribution of soil organic carbon and its relation to climate and vegetation. *Belowground Processes and Global Change* **10**, 423–436 (2000).
3. Paustian, K. *et al.* Climate-smart soils. *Nature* **532**, 49–57 (2016).
4. Minasny, B. *et al.* Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma* **292**, 59–86 (2017).
5. Bossio, D. A. *et al.* The role of soil carbon in natural climate solutions. *Nature Sustainability* (2020) doi:10.1038/s41893-020-0491-z.
6. Amelung, W. *et al.* Towards a global-scale soil climate mitigation strategy. *Nature Communications* **11**, 1–10 (2020).
7. Lützw, M. V. *et al.* Stabilization of organic matter in temperate soils: Mechanisms and their relevance under different soil conditions - A review. *European Journal of Soil Science* **57**, 426–445 (2006).
8. Schmidt, M. W. I. *et al.* Persistence of soil organic matter as an ecosystem property. *Nature* **478**, 49–56 (2011).
9. Peixoto, L. *et al.* Deep-rooted perennial crops differ in capacity to stabilize C inputs in deep soil layers. *Sci Rep* **12**, 5952 (2022).
10. Thorup-Kristensen, K. *et al.* Digging Deeper for Agricultural Resources, the Value of Deep Rooting. *Trends in Plant Science* **25**, 406–417 (2020).
11. Button, E. S. *et al.* Deep-C storage: Biological, chemical and physical strategies to enhance carbon stocks in agricultural subsoils. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **170**, 108697 (2022).
12. Kuzyakov, Y., Friedel, J. K. & Stahr, K. Review of mechanisms and quantification of priming effects. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **14** (2000).
13. Blagodatskaya, E. & Kuzyakov, Y. Mechanisms of real and apparent priming effects and their dependence on soil microbial biomass and community structure: critical review. *Biol Fertil Soils* **45**, 115–131 (2008).
14. Guttières, R. *et al.* Temperature and soil management effects on carbon fluxes and priming effect intensity. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **153**, 108103 (2021).
15. Chen, L. *et al.* Regulation of priming effect by soil organic matter stability over a broad geographic scale. *Nat Commun* **10**, 5112 (2019).
16. Lyu, M. *et al.* Simulated leaf litter addition causes opposite priming effects on natural forest and plantation soils. *Biol Fertil Soils* **54**, 925–934 (2018).
17. Siles, J. A. *et al.* Priming effects in soils across Europe. *Global Change Biology* gcb.16062 (2022) doi:10.1111/gcb.16062.
18. Luo, Z., Wang, E. & Sun, O. J. A meta-analysis of the temporal dynamics of priming soil carbon decomposition by fresh carbon inputs across ecosystems. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **101**, 96–103 (2016).
19. Bastida, F. *et al.* Global ecological predictors of the soil priming effect. *Nat Commun* **10**, 3481 (2019).
20. Gaudel, G. *et al.* Meta-analysis of the priming effect on native soil organic carbon in response to glucose amendment across soil depths. *Plant Soil* (2021) doi:10.1007/s11104-021-05168-5.
21. Fontaine, S. *et al.* Stability of organic carbon in deep soil layers controlled by fresh carbon supply. *Nature* **450**, 277–280 (2007).
22. Fontaine, S., Bardoux, G., Abbadie, L. & Mariotti, A. Carbon input to soil may decrease soil carbon content. *Ecology Letters* **7**, 314–320 (2004).
23. Bernard, L. *et al.* Advancing the mechanistic understanding of the priming effect on soil organic matter mineralisation. *Functional Ecology* 1365-2435.14038 (2022) doi:10.1111/1365-2435.14038.
24. Guenet, B. *et al.* Impact of priming on global soil carbon stocks. *Glob Change Biol* **24**, 1873–1883 (2018).

25. Wordell-Dietrich, P., Don, A. & Helfrich, M. Controlling factors for the stability of subsoil carbon in a Dystric Cambisol. *Geoderma* **304**, 40–48 (2017).
26. Hicks Pries, C. E. *et al.* Root litter decomposition slows with soil depth. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **125**, 103–114 (2018).
27. Kuzyakov, Y. Review: Factors affecting rhizosphere priming effects. *Journal Plant Nutrition Soil Science* **15** (2002).
28. Kuzyakov, Y. & Blagodatskaya, E. Microbial hotspots and hot moments in soil: Concept & review. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **83**, 184–199 (2015).
29. Huo, C., Luo, Y. & Cheng, W. Rhizosphere priming effect: A meta-analysis. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **111**, 78–84 (2017).
30. Dijkstra, F. A., Zhu, B. & Cheng, W. Root effects on soil organic carbon: a double-edged sword. *New Phytol* **230**, 60–65 (2021).
31. Kuzyakov, Y. & Razavi, B. S. Rhizosphere size and shape: Temporal dynamics and spatial stationarity. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **135**, 343–360 (2019).
32. Kleber, M. *et al.* Dynamic interactions at the mineral–organic matter interface. *Nat Rev Earth Environ* (2021) doi:10.1038/s43017-021-00162-y.
33. Sokol, N. W. *et al.* Life and death in the soil microbiome: how ecological processes influence biogeochemistry. *Nat Rev Microbiol* (2022) doi:10.1038/s41579-022-00695-z.
34. Sokol, N. W. & Bradford, M. A. Microbial formation of stable soil carbon is more efficient from belowground than aboveground input. *Nature Geoscience* **12**, 46–53 (2019).
35. Jilling, A., Keiluweit, M., Gutknecht, J. L. M. & Grandy, A. S. Priming mechanisms providing plants and microbes access to mineral-associated organic matter. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **158**, 108265 (2021).
36. Schiedung, M., Tregurtha, C. S., Beare, M. H., Thomas, S. M. & Don, A. Deep soil flipping increases carbon stocks of New Zealand grasslands. *Glob Change Biol* **25**, 2296–2309 (2019).
37. Alcántara, V., Don, A., Vesterdal, L., Well, R. & Nieder, R. Stability of buried carbon in deep-ploughed forest and cropland soils - implications for carbon stocks. *Scientific Reports* **7**, 5511 (2017).
38. Pereira, R. C. *et al.* Evidence for soil carbon enhancement through deeper mouldboard ploughing at pasture renovation on a Typic Fragiaqualf. *Soil Res.* **56**, 182 (2018).
39. Kirschbaum, M. U. F. *et al.* Sequestration of soil carbon by burying it deeper within the profile: A theoretical exploration of three possible mechanisms. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **163**, 108432 (2021).
40. Alcántara, V., Don, A., Well, R. & Nieder, R. Deep ploughing increases agricultural soil organic matter stocks. *Global change biology* **22**, 2939–2956 (2016).
41. Sanauallah, M. *et al.* How do microbial communities in top- and subsoil respond to root litter addition under field conditions? *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **103**, 28–38 (2016).
42. Cookson, W. R., Beare, M. H. & Wilson, P. E. Effects of prior crop residue management on microbial properties and crop residue decomposition. *Applied Soil Ecology* **7**, 179–188 (1998).
43. Don, A., Böhme, I. H., Dohrmann, A. B., Poeplau, C. & Tebbe, C. C. Microbial community composition affects soil organic carbon turnover in mineral soils. *Biology and Fertility of Soils* **53**, 445–456 (2017).
44. Lehmann, J. *et al.* Persistence of soil organic carbon caused by functional complexity. *Nature Geoscience* **13**, 529–534 (2020).
45. Fontaine, S., Mariotti, A. & Abbadie, L. The priming effect of organic matter: a question of microbial competition? *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **35**, 837–843 (2003).
46. Kögel-Knabner, I. *et al.* Organo-mineral associations in temperate soils: Integrating biology, mineralogy, and organic matter chemistry. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science* **171**, 61–82 (2008).
47. Lehmann, J. & Kleber, M. The contentious nature of soil organic matter. *Nature* **528**, 60–68 (2015).
48. Gregorich, E. G., Beare, M. H., McKim, U. F. & Skjemstad, J. O. Chemical and Biological Characteristics of Physically Uncomplexed Organic Matter. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* **70**, 975–985 (2006).

49. Villarino, S. H., Pinto, P., Jackson, R. B. & Piñeiro, G. Plant rhizodeposition: A key factor for soil organic matter formation in stable fractions. *Sci. Adv.* **7**, eabd3176 (2021).
50. Poeplau, C., Don, A. & Schneider, F. Roots are key to increasing the mean residence time of organic carbon entering temperate agricultural soils. *GCB* **27**, 4921–4934 (2021).
51. Fossum, C. *et al.* Belowground allocation and dynamics of recently fixed plant carbon in a California annual grassland. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **165**, 108519 (2022).
52. Sanderman, J., Creamer, C., Baisden, W. T., Farrell, M. & Fallon, S. Greater soil carbon stocks and faster turnover rates with increasing agricultural productivity. *Soil* **3**, 1–16 (2017).
53. Angst, G., Kögel-Knabner, I., Kirfel, K., Hertel, D. & Mueller, C. W. Spatial distribution and chemical composition of soil organic matter fractions in rhizosphere and non-rhizosphere soil under European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.). *Geoderma* **264**, 179–187 (2016).
54. Shi, A. *et al.* Substrate spatial heterogeneity reduces soil microbial activity. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **152**, 108068 (2021).
55. Nunan, N., Leloup, J., Ruamps, L. S., Pouteau, V. & Chenu, C. Effects of habitat constraints on soil microbial community function. *Sci Rep* **7**, 4280 (2017).
56. Inagaki, T. M. *et al.* Microscale spatial distribution and soil organic matter persistence in top and subsoil. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **178**, 108921 (2023).
57. Lawrence-Smith, E. J. *et al.* Full inversion tillage during pasture renewal to increase soil carbon storage: New Zealand as a case study. *GCB* **27**, 1998–2010 (2021).

Methods

Study sites and soil samples. Soils were sampled in October to November 2017 at the West Coast of New Zealand's South Island in the Cape Foulwind region (as described in ref.³⁶). The region is characterized by a temperate climate with warm summers (Köppen-Geiger: Cfb) with high annual precipitation (2,000-3,000 mm) and alluvial and marine deposits as parent material. These conditions promote the formation of highly developed Podzol soils, which are the dominant soil type. Intense iron pan formation causes water logging of the upper soil. To improve the productivity of these soils and to obtain high productive pasture, deep soil inversion (full inversion to 1-3 m) is used to break iron pans and increase drainage. This inversion causes a translocation of former topsoils into subsoil regions and the creation of new surface soils, which are depleted in SOC. Following the inversion and topsoil preparation, perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.) and white clover (*Trifolium repens* L.) were sown and the sites were managed as high-production pastures. Grazing interval range between three and four weeks with an average stocking rate of 2.85 animals ha⁻¹. Synthetic fertilizer (320–500 kg N ha⁻¹, 40–120 kg P ha⁻¹, 80 kg K ha⁻¹, 70–180 kg S ha⁻¹) and lime (3 t ha⁻¹) were applied annually⁵⁸. The cultivation, fertilizer and lime application were similar for non-inverted and inverted soils over the years except for higher capital fertilizer applications in the first year after inversion.

A chronosequence of sites were sampled (15 cm increments to 210 cm maximum depth), including non-inverted soils and soils inverted 3, 7, 13 and 20 years prior to sampling. From each site, topsoils (0-15 cm) and subsoils (30-210 cm depending on inversion depth) were composited from three replicates per depth obtained from one soil pit per time step (Table S1). All soils were classified as loamy sand (77 ± 6% sand, 18 ± 5% silt, and 4 ± 1% clay) with similar pH values (4.5 ± 0.3) and similar oxalate extractable amorphous poorly crystalline Fe and Al (Fe: 0.1-0.3 wt% and Al: 0.1-0.5 wt%) contents³⁶. Additional X-ray fluorescence (XRF, XEPOS HE, SPECTRO Analytical Instruments, Germany) analyses supported similar elemental compositions: 6.08 ± 0.51 wt% total Al, 2.46 ± 0.23 wt% total Fe and

0.12 ± 0.02 wt% Mn as averages of all samples. Milled samples were used for the XRF analyses in powder cups and an international reference material was used as a standard (NCS DC 73319/73326). The similar soil properties and composition along the chronosequence allowed to gain an understanding of priming responses within the 20 years of topsoil development and subsoil SOC enrichment.

The inversion resulted in SOC stock increases by 69 ± 15% (179 ± 40 Mg SOC ha⁻¹) in 0-150 cm depth over 20 years due to the burial and a SOC accumulation of 1.2-1.8 Mg SOC (ha year)⁻¹ in the upper 0-15 cm³⁶. The topsoil SOC was highest in the non-inverted soil (61.1 mg SOC (g soil)⁻¹) and increased from 3-20 years after inversion (9.5-28.0 mg SOC (g soil)⁻¹). The subsoil SOC content was lowest in the non-inverted soil (9.5 mg SOC (g soil)⁻¹) and ranged in inverted subsoils between 11.6-44.0 mg SOC (g soil)⁻¹ (Table S1).

Microbial biomass. To determine microbial biomass (C_{mic}), three replicates of 50 g air dried samples were conditioned to 35-50% water holding capacity (WHC) and pre-incubated for two weeks at 22°C and substrate induced respiration (SIR) was used as described by ref.⁵⁹. The determination of C_{mic} was performed in February 2018 using the stored samples. In brief, 0.5 g of glucose-talcum mixture (30% glucose, resulting in 3000 µg glucose (g dry soil)⁻¹) was blended in the sample by gently mixing with an electric hand stirrer for 20-30 sec. The evolving CO₂ was measured for 12 hours in a semi-automatic continuous flow system⁶⁰ with an air flow of 250 ml min⁻¹, using an infrared gas analyzer (ADC-255-MK3, Analytical Development Co. Ltd., Hoddesdon, UK) for hourly CO₂ measurements. All steps were performed in the same order and similar disturbance (e.g. mixing soil) for every sample to allow the direct comparison. The C_{mic} was calculated by multiplying the maximum initial respiration rate obtained by SIR with a conversion factor of 30, as recommended by ref.⁶¹.

Input of ¹³C labeled root-derived biomass. All soil samples were stored after sampling and dried at 40°C until the start of the incubation experiment in September 2020. For each soil, two aluminum containers (20x13 cm and 6 cm height) were packed with 150 g dry and <2 mm soil, resulting in approx. 2 cm soil cover. The soils were covered with a 2 mm nylon mesh. On one of each soil boxes, 12 g of ryegrass seeds (*Lolium perenne* L) were applied and covered with 115 g of washed and combusted lightweight expanded clay aggregates (8-12 mm size) to allow a better germination of the grass. The same quantity of lightweight expanded clay aggregates was applied on the control box which did not receive any ryegrass seeds (Extended Data Figure 1). All soils were pre-incubated for 22 days at 25°C in the multi-isotope controlled environment facility at the University of Zurich⁶². The soils with ryegrass seeds were pre-incubated under a continuous 10 atom% ¹³C enriched atmosphere and 8-12 hrs of light per day emitted by a plasma lamp reflecting the solar spectra (Lumixo, Lumatrix SA) with an intensity of 1000 W m⁻². The ryegrass was not cut during the pre-incubation period and regularly (at 18 days) watered with the same amount of water (15-60 ml) per soil box. All soils were incubated in the same labeling chamber to maintain similar light, moisture and temperature conditions during the pre-incubation and achieve similar inputs of root-derived C. The control soils were incubated in the dark and ambient atmosphere at the same temperature. Prior to the pre-incubation, the water extractable nitrate and ammonium was determined (1:5 soil to water solution, 1h shaking) by photometric measurement (LCK 304 Ammonium and LCK 339 Nitrate using a DR 1900 photometer, Hach Lange, Germany). The total nitrate and ammonium bound nitrogen (N) ranged between 0.05-0.39wt% N. In order to allow a similar growth of the ryegrass and avoid N limitations, the available N was adjusted to 0.42 wt% N soil by adding ammonium-nitrate (5 atom% ¹⁵N labeled, Sigma-Aldrich) dissolved in 60 ml deionized water. The control soils received 60 ml deionized water without any additional N. The soil moisture was adjusted regularly to the initial soil moisture of the pre-incubation.

After the pre-incubation, the aboveground biomass was removed, and its dry mass was determined which varied between 2.2-3.7 g per soil box. To achieve a maximum input of belowground biomass and avoid input of aboveground biomass, the 2 mm mesh was carefully lifted, and the roots were cut close to the soil surface. Seeds and lightweight expanded clay aggregates, which fell on the soil, were removed manually. In order to homogenize roots and soil, roots were cut in the soil with scissors into pieces of about 1-0.5 cm for 1.5 minutes. Afterwards the soil and roots were mixed for one additional minute using a spoon. The lightweight expanded clay and the 2 mm mesh were also removed from the control soils and the soils were mixed for 2.5 minutes to ensure a similar degree of disturbance. The removal of the aboveground biomass, the cutting of roots and mixing was conducted stepwise for each sample and the homogenized samples were directly separated into four replicates for the closed jar incubation (see section *Closed jar incubation*), which was started within 30 minutes to avoid losses of rapidly respired C after disturbance. Therefore, we considered here four incubation replicates that received the same amount and quality of root-derived organic matter. As they are derived from the same pre-incubated soil, they need to be considered as pseudoreplicates. The pre-incubation with growing ryegrass resulted in an average total C input to the soil by roots of 3.3 ± 0.8 mg C g⁻¹ soil, ranging between 2.5-5.2 mg C g⁻¹ soil (Table S1). The total root-derived C inputs were calculated by using mixing calculations based on the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the pre-incubated bulk soils (as described below). There was no significant difference of root-derived C input between topsoils and subsoils (t-test p-value=0.88). Furthermore, the distribution of added root-derived C between coarse roots (>2 mm) and fine soil fractions (<2 mm) was similar for all soils (Fig. S3 and Table S2). The root input here by fresh ryegrass was dominated by coarse roots. However, this approach also includes ryegrass derived inputs of potentially fast cycling roots exudates originated from the living roots prior to the biomass removal. The initial CO₂-C fluxes induced by exudates and labile compounds were captured here by starting the closed jar incubation right after the biomass removal as described above.

Closed jar incubation. The pre-incubated soils were adjusted to 60% WHC in the boxes used for the pre-incubation. The moist soil was divided into five equal subsamples, which corresponded to approx. 30 g dry soil mass each. Four of these five subsamples were incubated as laboratory pseudoreplicates in sterilized glass beakers, each placed in a separate 2 l airtight glass jar to measure heterotrophic soil respiration. The remaining subsample was used for further analysis and SOC fractionation. The incubation was conducted at 25°C in the dark using closed incubators (MIR-554-PE, Panasonic Healthcare Co., Japan). Each glass jar contained a glass vial of 40 ml of deionized water to avoid drying of the headspace and 20-30 ml of a 1 M NaOH solution in brown glass vials to capture CO₂-C evolving during the mineralization. The NaOH traps were replaced and sampled after 1, 3, 10, 30, 63, 100 and 164 days after the start of the incubation. The amount of trapped CO₂-C was determined by measuring the decrease in electrical conductivity of the NaOH solution according to ref.⁶³. For the first ten days, the jars were checked daily, and re-growing ryegrass was removed immediately with minimal soil disturbance. No re-growth was observed after ten days, and autotrophic respiration was neglectable. The soil moisture was adjusted to the initial moisture content after 30 days. After 164 days, the gravimetric moisture content was on average $8.2 \pm 0.4\%$ lower compared to the initial moisture content. Two additional jars were prepared with a mix of each topsoil (control and ¹³C labeled separately) to monitor the electrical conductivity of the NaOH traps and to avoid CO₂-C saturation of the traps. Four jars without any soil were incubated as blanks for background correction of the measured electrical conductivity.

Sample preparation and analysis. The electrical conductivity of the NaOH traps was measured in [mS cm⁻¹] using an electrical conductivity meter (914 pH/Conductometer, Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland). The temperature of the traps of the first and last sample was measured (with 0.1°C precision) to correct temperature dependent changes in electrical conductivity. To

determine the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the captured $\text{CO}_2\text{-C}$, 2.5 ml of each NaOH trap solution were mixed with 5 ml of a 1 M SrCl_2 solution to precipitate SrCO_3 . After centrifugation (1,000xg; 5 min), the supernatant was decanted and the precipitated SrCO_3 was dried at 50°C.

The soils with ^{13}C root addition were wet sieved to 2 mm using an aerosol pressure bottle to separate the grown roots (>2mm) from the soil. On average, 140.6 ± 14.9 mg of roots were separated after the pre-incubation, which represented 0.4-1.4% of the dry weight. The roots and the soils were dried at 40°C. Four independent aliquots of the dried roots from the pre-incubated soils were selected by hand to determine the ^{13}C label of the added roots which was used for the recovery calculations of the labeled ^{13}C in the respired $\text{CO}_2\text{-C}$, SOC fractions and bulk soils. A magnifying glass was used to ensure that no mineral phase was associated with the root organic matter, which would have diluted the measured root $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.

The SOC fractionation of the pre-incubated and incubated soils was performed by using the density and particle size fractionation approach presented by ref.⁶⁴ and the improved protocol described by ref.⁶⁵. For the pre-incubated soil, 12-20 g were fractionated. The soils of the four incubation replicates were composited by weight (5 g each) and 20 g were fractionated of each topsoil and subsoil. Two fractions were considered as particulate organic matter (POM; lighter than 1.6 g cm^{-3}) and mineral associated organic matter (MAOM; heavier than 1.6 g cm^{-3}). The MAOM consisted of two particle fractions with a threshold of 63 μm , but these were summarized here (Fig. S2). Total mass recoveries were $99 \pm 1\%$ and total SOC recoveries were $95 \pm 2\%$ as average of all samples.

The total C and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ relative to the international Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite standard (VPDB) of all soils, SOC fractions and SrCO_3 samples were measured using a dry combustion module cavity ring-down spectroscopy system (Picarro, Santa Clara, USA).

Calculations and statistical analysis. The concentration of CO_2 ($[\text{CO}_2, \text{NaOH}]$) in $[\text{mg ml}^{-1}]$, trapped as NaCO_3 , was based on a calibration obtained by ref.⁶⁶ and calculated as:

$$[CO_{2;NaOH}] = -0.168 * EC_{NaOH;sample} + 28.639$$

Where $EC_{NaOH;sample}$ is the measured electrical conductivity of the NaOH trap [mS cm⁻¹] corrected to 25°C. The total respired CO₂-C (CO_2-C_{total}) in [mg] was calculated as:

$$CO_2-C_{total} = [CO_{2;NaOH}] * v_{NaOH} * 0.2729$$

Where v_{NaOH} is the volume of the NaOH trap [ml] and by considering the mass fraction of C. The root-derived C in bulk soil, the respired CO₂-C and the SOC fractions were calculated with the atomic ¹³C fraction as presented in ref. ⁶⁷. The isotope-amount ratios $R(^{13}C/^{12}C)_{sample}$ were calculated for each sample (using $R(^{13}C/^{12}C)_{VPDB} = 0.01118$). The atomic fraction $x(^{13}C)_{sample}$ was calculated for each sample as:

$$x(^{13}C)_{sample} = \frac{R(^{13}C/^{12}C)_{sample}}{1 + R(^{13}C/^{12}C)_{sample}}$$

The excess-isotopic-amount $xE(^{13}C)_{sample}$ was calculated as

$$xE(^{13}C)_{sample} = x(^{13}C)_{sample} - x(^{13}C)_{control}$$

Where $x(^{13}C)_{control}$ is the atomic fraction of the soil, SOC fractions and respired CO₂ of the treatments without ¹³C-roots. The proportion of root-derived C, f_{root} , of each sample was calculated as:

$$f_{root} = \frac{xE(^{13}C)_{sample}}{xE(^{13}C)_{root}}$$

where $xE(^{13}C)_{root}$ is the excess-isotopic-amount fraction of the root >2 mm of each treatment (Table 1). The f_{root} of each sample was used to calculate the absolute amount of root-derived C in the respired CO₂ and in the SOC fractions. The amount of native SOC of each sample was calculated as the difference between the total measured C and the corresponding root-derived C. The recoveries of total SOC, native SOC and root-derived C were on average $96 \pm 9\%$ for the roots >2mm, the respired CO₂ and the SOC fractions.

The relative priming effect (PE) and additional native SOC respiration was calculated by the differences of total respiration measured from controls without roots and the native SOC calculated for each treatment as:

$$PE = \frac{CO_2-C_{native\ SOC; sample} - CO_2-C_{control}}{CO_2-C_{control}} \times 100\%$$

where $CO_2-C_{native\ SOC; sample}$ is the total respired CO_2 -C after the incubation derived from native SOC of each sample in [mg] and $CO_2-C_{control}$ is the total respired CO_2 -C derived from control treatments in [mg].

All statistical analyses were performed using R Studio (Version 1.3.1073, ref.⁶⁸). To test significant differences between CO_2 production (total, specific per SOC, native SOC and root-derived C) with time since inversion, linear models were applied and p-values were computed on a 95% pairwise confidence interval with a post hoc-test (Tukey) and a Bonferroni multiplicity adjustment by using the multcomp package⁶⁹. Shapiro-Wilk tests were used to test the data for normal distribution and log-transformation was applied to reach normality if needed. Differences between topsoil and subsoil, as well as total remaining root-derived C and respired native SOC were computed using Welch two sample t-tests (Table S4 & S5).

Data availability

All data published in this manuscript is accessible on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7304562).

Method-only References

58. Thomas, S. M., Beare, M. H. & Rietveld, V. Changes in soil quality following humping/hollowing and flipping of pakihī soils on the West Coast, South Island New Zealand. *New Zealand Grassland Association Sixty-ninth Conference* 265–270 (2007).
59. Anderson, J. P. E. & Domsch, K. H. A physiological method for the quantitative measurement of microbial biomass in soils. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **10**, 215–221 (1978).
60. Heinemeyer, O., Insam, H., Kaiser, E. A. & Walenzik, G. Soil microbial biomass and respiration measurements: An automated technique based on infra-red gas analysis. *Plant and Soil* **195**, 191–195 (1989).

61. Kaiser, E. A., Mueller, T., Joergensen, R. G., Insam, H. & Heinemeyer, O. Evaluation of methods to estimate the soil microbial biomass and the relationship with soil texture and organic matter. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* **24**, 675–683 (1992).
62. Studer, M. S. *et al.* The MICE facility—a new tool to study plant–soil C cycling with a holistic approach. *Isotopes in Environmental and Health Studies* **53**, 286–297 (2017).
63. Wollum, A. G. & Gomez, J. E. A Conductivity Method for Measuring Microbially Evolved Carbon Dioxide. *Ecology* **51**, 155–156 (1970).
64. Zimmermann, M., Leifeld, J., Schmidt, M. W. I., Smith, P. & Fuhrer, J. Measured soil organic matter fractions can be related to pools in the RothC model. *European Journal of Soil Science* **58**, 658–667 (2007).
65. Poeplau, C. *et al.* Reproducibility of a soil organic carbon fractionation method to derive RothC carbon pools. *European Journal of Soil Science* **64**, 735–746 (2013).
66. Abiven, S. & Andreoli, R. Charcoal does not change the decomposition rate of mixed litters in a mineral cambisol: A controlled conditions study. *Biology and Fertility of Soils* **47**, 111–114 (2011).
67. Coplen, T. B. Guidelines and recommended terms for expression of stable-isotope-ratio and gas-ratio measurement results. *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry* **25**, 2538–2560 (2011).
68. R Core Team. R Studio. (2021).
69. Hothorn, T. *et al.* Multcomp package: Simultaneous inference in general parametric models (Version1.4-17). (2021).

Extended Data

Extended Data Figure 1 | Soil inversion and input of labeled roots. Concept of soil inversion (**a**) showing the non-inverted soil with SOC-rich topsoil. The inversion brings the former topsoil in the new subsoil and a new topsoil is created consisting of former subsoil. Set up of pre-incubation and growth of ryegrass under ¹³C enriched environment (10 atm%) to achieve highly labeled root input (**b**). The ryegrass seeds were placed on a 2 mm nylon mesh (black dotted line) to allow germination into the soil. After 22 days, aboveground biomass was removed directly at the mesh and soils were mixed prior to the division into the four replicates (equal weight) used for the closed jar incubation (**c**). The roots were cut during homogenization into 0.5-1 cm large pieces. The respired CO₂ was trapped in NaOH traps to determine the total respiration by conductivity. By determining the isotopic composition of the trapped CO₂ (precipitated as SrCO₃), the contribution of native SOC and root-derived C was calculated (see method section). The isotopic signature of the root-derived C allowed to trace it in the soils and within SOC fraction separated as particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral associated organic matter (MAOM; divided in sand & aggregate (> 63 μm) and silt & clay (<63 μm) particle sizes).

Extended Data Figure 2 | Total CO₂ production six months of incubation. The cumulative total CO₂-C production is shown per mass of soil (**a** & **b**) and the specific production is given per total SOC, including native SOC and root-derived C (**c** & **d**). All values are presented with the standard error of the mean of incubation replicates (n=4, also shown as circles). Significant differences between the years since inversion were identified by analysis of variance (ANOVA) and p-values were computed on a 95% pairwise confidence interval with a post hoc-test (Tukey) and a Bonferroni multiplicity adjustment as indicated by letters (p<0.05). All p-values are presented in Table S6 and S7. The cumulative fluxes over the incubation time are shown in Fig. S1.

Extended Data Figure 3 | Native SOC and root-derived C specific CO_2 production. Cumulative CO_2 production over six months as native SOC specific $[\text{mg CO}_2\text{-C}_{\text{native SOC}} (\text{g native SOC})^{-1}]$ respiration (a), root-derived C specific $[\text{mg CO}_2\text{-C}_{\text{root-derived SOC}} (\text{g root-derived C})^{-1}]$ (b) respiration and proportion of root-derived C ($\text{CO}_2\text{-C}_{\text{root-derived}}$) of total respired $\text{CO}_2\text{-C}$ at each timestep (c) for topsoil and subsoils. Error bars indicate the propagated standard error of the mean over the days of incubation of the incubation replicates ($n=4$).

Extended Data Figure 4 | Priming effect in inverted soils with roots. Additional native SOC respiration of inverted soils (3-20 years) with fitted two-tailed linear regression over time since inversion for topsoils (**a**; $R^2=0.66$, $p<0.001$) and subsoils (**b**; $R^2=0.14$, $p=0.09$). Grey linear model for subsoils (**b**; $R^2=0.96$, $p<0.001$) shows the fit excluding the soil inverted seven years ago.

Extended Data Figure 5 | Incubated root-derived C in particulate organic matter. Proportion of root-derived C remained after the incubation in the particulate organic matter (POM) fraction. The proportion of root derived C after the growth (pre-incubation) and before the incubation are shown in Tab. S2. Linear models with time since inversion are shown in Fig. S5.